

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
facility

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ABSTRACT

This document outlines a comprehensive methodology for collecting, storing and managing the data provided by the measurements of the experiments conducted in the 6G-SANDBOX framework. The methodology encompasses the necessary tools and processes required to capture the data generated in each test, process it and transform into useful information that can be analyzed afterwards. To support this approach three tools have been deployed each playing a critical role in ensuring the effective handling and utilisation of experimental data:

1. Campaign Manager
2. Application KPIs repository
3. Experiment Life Cycle Manager

This document also includes the information related to the current open dataset repositories for each project platform: Athens, Oulu, Berlin and Malaga.

KEYWORDS

Repository, Data-set, Measurements, Experimentation, Campaign Manager, ELCM, NaC, InfluxDB, KPI, API

1 INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of mobile communications, the transition to 6G networks represents a significant technological leap, characterized by high data rates, reduced latency, and enhanced connectivity. To fully leverage these advancements, it is imperative to continuously refine network architectures and technologies through rigorous research and experimentation. This document introduces the process to create the open repository of measurement results, which forms a core part of 6G-SANDBOX project. The repository is intended to serve as a valuable resource for researchers, network architects, and technology developers. It offers access to empirical data spanning a wide range of scenarios.

The project involves deploying trial networks specifically designed to test, measure and evaluate various aspects of 5G and B5G technologies on the road to 6G. This document begins by detailing the process of data generation, describing how measurements are collected from these trial networks.

Subsequently, the document delves into the tools that generate the data provided from the experiments. Three tools are utilised to manage the data generation process:

1. Campaign Manager. It is an automation tool that drives and collects all the test results generated by the Keysight solutions deployed in 6G-SANDBOX.
2. Application KPIs storage through a Network as Code (NaC) server. It provides a mechanism to store and retrieve KPIs at application level linked to any experiment run in the trial network. To ease the operation to any stakeholder the NaC paradigm is applied: it is an approach that applies the principles of infrastructure as code (IaC) to network management and operations, particularly in the context of advanced networking environments like 5G mobile networks. This paradigm involves managing and provisioning network devices and services through machine-readable definition files, rather than through physical hardware configurations or interactive configuration tools. This shift allows for more automated, programmable, and consistent network operations.
3. Experiment Life Cycle Manager (ELCM). It is a key component of the experimentation framework that manages the life cycle of experiments conducted on the trial networks. It handles the orchestration, deployment, monitoring, and termination of experiments, ensuring efficient and automated processes.

Afterwards, the document gives information about the current data sets being utilised in 6G-SANDBOX across the four platforms namely Athens, Oulu, Berlin and Malaga.

By providing a comprehensive overview of the repository's creation, structure, and management, this document aims to serve as a foundational reference for stakeholders involved in the development of 5G/6G technologies as well as those seeking to understand the complexities of implementing and utilizing an open experimentation facility in the context of mobile networks. The document also reports how 6G-SANDBOX is implementing data generation through the experimental process from experiments.

A further step beyond data generation is data publication and exploitation. In this regard, 6G-SANDBOX has started an activity towards providing a uniform way to expose results from experimentation across SNS projects. The ambition of this activity is to progress on standard formats

for describing experiments (network scenarios and experimental procedures) and experimentation data (both input and output), as well as to develop governance models that extend beyond basic IPR management. Such an approach will benefit from all the current activities in Data Spaces, where projects like SLICES and GAIA-X are active. Current activity in 6G-SANDBOX is the analysis of potential reusable results from these projects and the setup of a proof of concept at University of Malaga with a connection to Malaga platform. The results will be included in deliverable D5.4 and pushed to the SNS JU TMV WG.

2 FROM MEASUREMENT TO DATA

In the context of the trial networks deployed by the TLNCM, InfluxDB was chosen as the database for the ELCM to store the measurements obtained during an experiment. The choice was made for several reasons that align with the specific requirements of a test and measurement framework, which are described below:

- **Time-Series Data Handling:** InfluxDB is specifically designed for storing and querying time-series data. Test and measurement data typically include timestamps and require efficient time-based querying and analysis. In addition, InfluxDB can handle high volumes of data writes efficiently, which is crucial for test environments where large amounts of data are generated rapidly.
- **Performance:** InfluxDB is optimized for fast query performance on time-series data, which is essential for real-time monitoring and quick analysis in testing environments. InfluxDB also uses efficient data compression techniques, which reduce the storage footprint and improve the performance of data retrieval operations.
- **Flexibility and Ease of Use:** InfluxDB provides schema flexibility, allowing users to add new types of data without the need for extensive schema modifications. This is beneficial in dynamic testing environments where new parameters and metrics may be introduced frequently. The InfluxQL and Flux query languages offer powerful querying capabilities, enabling complex data analysis and aggregation with relative ease.
- **Integration Capabilities:** InfluxDB integrates smoothly with various tools and platforms commonly used in the test and measurement industry, such as Grafana for visualization and other data processing tools. This integration capability enhances the overall functionality and usability of the experimentation framework. Moreover, InfluxDB supports multiple data ingestion protocols, including HTTP, MQTT, and others, making it easier to collect data from diverse sources and devices used in testing setups.
- **Community and Support:** InfluxDB has an active open-source community and offers commercial support options. This ensures that users can get help and access resources when needed, reducing the risk of adopting and integrating the database into their workflows.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** The open-source version of InfluxDB provides a cost-effective solution for many use cases, while the enterprise version offers additional features and support for organizations with more demanding requirements.

The measurements collected during the experiments executed inside the trial network, are stored in the InfluxDB with each entry tagged using the same ExecutionID and the identifier of the Trial Network. The content of the database is not predefined as it depends on the specific use case under test and the resources used for executing the test case. In general terms, the data is organized into measurements, tags, and fields:

- A measurement is a collection of related data points.

- Tags are indexed key-value pairs that are used to store metadata.
- Fields are key-value pairs that store the actual data values. Fields are not indexed and are typically used for storing metrics.
- Timestamps. Each data point in the InfluxDB includes a timestamp, which is used to track when the data was collected. Timestamps are automatically indexed.

There are only two mandatory tags, the ExecutionId, and the TrialNetworkId. These tags enable the linking of all measurements corresponding to the same experiment in a given trial network.

The nature of the data stored in the database can encompass both raw data and already calculated Key Performance Indicators depending on the probes and resources available within the trial network.

Raw data typically includes all the unprocessed measurements directly captured from test instruments. This can result in a high volume of data points due to the detailed and frequent logging of test parameters. Raw data is highly granular, providing detailed insights into every aspect of the test environment. Each data point is often timestamped, capturing the state of the system at precise moments. Consequently, raw data allows maximum flexibility in post-processing, enabling various analyses and KPI calculations.

For example, if the trial network includes a data analytic tool that computes some KPIs related to the use case, these KPIs will also be injected into the InfluxDB with the ExecutionID and the TrialNetworkID tags.

The data stored in the local influx DB available in the trial networks, will be used as input in the global Open Data Structure that will be created by the project.

3 DATA GENERATION TOOLS

In the following subsections the three deployed tools in charge of generating data in 6G-SANDBOX are described.

3.1 CAMPAIGN MANAGER

3.1.1 INTRODUCTION

This section provides a summary of the data sources coming from the campaign manager. The campaign manager is the overall test automation solution based on the Campaign manager from Keysight (KS8500) built on top of [OpenTAP™](#). It orchestrates and collects all test results from the Keysight solutions deployed in 6G-SANDBOX. This section here should be read in conjunction with section 3.1 from D5.1, which provides a detailed description of all the elements mentioned here below.

The Campaign Manager is a public cloud-based service in which test campaigns and test plans can be edited. The Campaign manager connects to the 6G-SANDBOX platforms by deploying an OpenTAP™ runner in the Trial network under test. Each Trial Network will therefore have its own runner. The runners can be seen at the campaign manager level according to the user's permission set. These runners connect locally to the necessary resources (T&M platforms and software) to execute the tests defined by the campaign manager. The Campaign manager has the dashboard view of the activities performed by the runners.

Results are collected by different instruments when running a test plan or a test campaign. The runner collects the information from the different instruments and stores this in the local platform data lake using an InfluxDB plugin.

3.1.2 RUNNERS

The campaign manager (KS8500) product is a cloud-based SaaS product. To allow access to local resources while executing tests, a Runner component can be deployed locally by the user, to execute test cases. Users can customize the runner's functionality by creating plugins, which are downloaded and executed by the runner as part of the test execution process.

In the framework of 6G-SANDBOX the runner is delivered as an Open Nebula component that creates and runs a docker image with the runner code, during the deployment. The Runner is part of the 6G-Library and available at https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/tree/campaign_manager_client

3.1.2.1 DEPLOYMENT

As mentioned previously, the Runner is deployed as an Open Nebula component. During deployment a docker image is created for the runner and the deployment automation scripts orchestrate the process. To accomplish this, access to the open tap package repository is required to retrieve the runner executable. Additionally, the component requires access to docker.io for deployment actions to obtain the base image, and to the APK repository to retrieve Docker.

URLs for connecting to instruments and the InfluxDB are configured by the KS8500 user and provisioned to the Runner.

Figure 1: Runner deployment approach

3.1.2.2 OUTPUT RESULTS

The Open Tap architecture (within the runner) uses a concept called Result Listener to capture and deliver output. The ResultListener class has virtual methods that are called during test plan execution.

When extending the ResultListener class, the following methods can be overwritten:

- `public override void OnTestPlanRunStart(TestPlanRun planRun)`
- `public override void OnTestStepRunStart(TestStepRun stepRun)`
- `public override void OnResultPublished(Guid stepRun, ResultTable result)`
- `public override void OnTestStepRunCompleted(TestStepRun stepRun)`
- `public override void OnTestPlanRunCompleted(TestPlanRun planRun, Stream logStream)`

These methods are called by OpenTAP and are guaranteed to be called in a certain order:

1. `OnTestPlanRunStart` – The method is called when the test plan starts, and all the resources have been opened (including Result Listeners). It then takes a `TestPlanRun` argument, containing parameters for the plan run.
2. `OnTestStepRunStart` – The method is called for each step when the step execution starts.
3. `OnResultPublished` – The method is called for each published result from the test step. This method is not called at all for test steps which do not publish any results.
4. `OnTestStepRunCompleted` – The method is called for each step when the step execution stops. At this point it is guaranteed that the test step does not publish more results.
5. `OnTestPlanRunCompleted` – The method is called when the test plan run finishes and it is invoked a single time during a test plan execution. The `TestPlanRun` object contains information regarding the run, including the duration and final verdict. The `LogStream` contains the log file produced by the plan run.

To illustrate the sequence of the above-mentioned methods, consider the following figure:

Figure 2: OpenTAP result output sequence

3.1.3 INFLUXDB PLUGIN

To allow the delivery of the test results into the platform data lake, the locally deployed Runner from the trial Network will leverage the InfluxDB plugin. This setup enables all test equipment connected to the runner to provide logs and measurement results. The InfluxDB Result Listener utilizing the concept described above in section 3.1.3 is integrated in the architecture as depicted in Figure 3.

The main advantage of this approach is that data is moved locally within the platform eliminating the need to pass large quantities of data to an external cloud service. Further, since the way the data is stored (data space) is still not fully defined, the plugin offers the flexibility to adapt the structure of how the data is stored. The implementation will be completed within the next few months.

Figure 3: InfluxDB OpenTAP plugin in the architecture

3.2 NAC SERVER

3.2.1 DESCRIPTION

The NaC server is a platform whereby the KPIs at application level of the experiments might be stored and retrieved. The platform is accessible by experimenters via an API. The whole platform is described below. First, its architecture is explained. Afterwards, how the software components were developed and deployed is clarified. Later, the hardware that run the software is listed. Lastly, details about the use of the API client are given.

3.2.1.1 NAC API FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE

The functional architecture of the Network as Code (NaC) API is depicted in the picture below:

Figure 4: NaC API functional architecture

The main components of the NaC API are the following:

- NaC server: responsible for the process that implements the NaC service as a REST API, whose endpoints are offered to clients via internet, after opening a VPN (OpenVPN). It is also connected to the 5G network and can operate with its different components (core network functions, radio modules, KPIs databases, etc), when required.
- NaC client: responsible for the process that consumes the NaC REST API endpoints. It is implemented as an object-oriented Python library and provides end users with a Python class that includes methods for invoking NaC services.
- CAPIF (3GPP Common Api Framework): is an integral part of the 3GPP specifications, it was defined to facilitate the network core exposure towards new application enablers. Currently it is used as a standardized API-management framework for secure and interoperable interaction between API providers and API consumers, and as such, facilitates the publication of the NaC API to the provider, and its consumption to interested third parties.
- KPI database: the Influx time-series database that stores and serves all the KPIs involved in NaC API activities.

3.2.1.2 SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The NaC server is implemented as a NodeJS application, connected to a MySQL database. Therefore, it requires a suitable platform to run Node applications and to host a MySQL database server. Nokia has deployed this NaC server and MySQL DB server on an virtual machine. The network interfaces of this machine are properly configured to allow access to the core nodes, the radio nodes, and the Influx database server that implements the KPI storage. An OpenVPN has also been created to allow secure access to the NaC server via the internet, therefore a VPN certificate must also be issued to every third party who wants to access the NaC server.

The CAPIF services have been implemented by Telefonica as a network of Docker containers. Nokia has deployed these CAPIF Docker containers on the same virtual machine that also hosts the NaC server and MySQL database server.

The NaC API must be published in CAPIF by the provider, and a security context has to be created in CAPIF for the provider, the NaC API, and every invoker (third party) that wants to consume it. Once this security context is created, the end user can access the NaC services using their NaC credentials, their CAPIF credentials and their CAPIF invoker ID.

The NaC client is implemented as an object-oriented Python library, which can be run from any node that executes Python scripts and reaches the NaC server, after opening the OpenVPN. The library is provided in the form of a wheel file that enables the installation of the NaC class along with all its dependencies.

Once the OpenVPN is established, the NaC client also communicates with the CAPIF services to obtain JWT access tokens. These tokens are then presented to the NaC server, which must validate them before granting access.

The KPI database is implemented as an Influx time-series database, complemented with Grafana for the presentation of the relevant information. Another component of the same suite, Telegraf, is also used for data collection. Nokia has deployed the InfluxDB and Grafana in a separate OpenStack virtual machine with Ubuntu Linux, while different Telegraf agents have been configured to be deployed as needed, particularly in the 5G cores.

3.2.1.3 HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

As previously explained, two separate OpenStack virtual machines have been provisioned, with the following characteristics:

- NaC server: 2 cores, 8Gb RAM, 60GB disk. OS Ubuntu 22.04 LTS.
- Influx & Grafana server: 8 cores, 8Gb RAM, 50GB disk. OS Ubuntu 20.04 LTS.

These features are those of the machines deployed by Nokia, but other configurations may apply.

3.2.1.4 NAC PYTHON API CLIENT

Source Code of the relevant methods of the NacApi class implemented in the NaC Python API client library can be found in Annex 1.

3.2.2 OUTPUT RESULTS

The output of NaC KPI-related methods is described in Annex 1 using example scripts.

3.3 ELCM

3.3.1 DESCRIPTION

The ELCM (Experiment Life Cycle Manager) is a key component of the experimentation framework that manages the life cycle of experiments conducted on the trial networks. It handles the orchestration, deployment, monitoring, and termination of experiments, ensuring efficient and automated processes. The ELCM offers experimenters a Web Portal to define and execute experiments, collect and analyze results, and iterate on experimental setups, thereby facilitating advanced research and testing in 5G topologies and configurations (see Figure 5 and Figure 6).

Figure 5: Web Portal for definition of the experiments.

Figure 6: Web Portal interface, access to executions logs and Grafana dashboard (Results)

The ELCM also provides a rest full API to initiate, cancel, and retrieve the experiment's status, among other actions. The full list of endpoints available is described in <https://github.com/6G->

[SANDBOX/ELCM/blob/main/docs/A1_ENDPOINTS.md](https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/ELCM/blob/main/docs/A1_ENDPOINTS.md). However, this interface is more oriented to automation or integration with other tools.

The ELCM is oriented to the execution of Test Cases, in different scenarios and may involve the usage of different user equipment (UEs). The Portal shown in Figure 5 provides a very simple interface to choose the test case or the test cases to be executed, as well as the scenario and the potential UEs involved. The experimenter can choose a combination of these features, and the Portal sends an Experiment Descriptor to the ELCM, which contains the selected parameters. In the ELCM, the test cases will be associated with a YML file that implements the selected test case. For the implementation of the test cases, there is a list of general tasks available, its description can be found at https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/ELCM/blob/main/docs/3-2a_GENERAL_TASKS.md. As an example, there are tasks that enable the execution of a bash or a TAP (Test Automation Platform) test plan. If the selection includes more than one test case, they will be executed one after the other. If the selection also includes more than one scenario, the ELCM will execute, sequentially, all the possible combinations of the test cases and the scenarios.

In the end, the tasks involve communication with the resources available in the trial network. For example, the monitoring probes available in the testbed have to be initiated, which means that the test case should include tasks that configure and start each probe required in the test case. To achieve this, an associated plugin that exposes the configuration and control interface of the resources is needed.

3.3.2 WORKFLOW

To introduce the workflow of the ELCM it can be seen as a scheduler for the execution of test cases. The execution of the test cases is based on the tasks previously mentioned, which are performed in three different stages:

- **Pre-Run:** This stage involves experiment registration and configuration, a feasibility check, and a wait loop for the necessary resources.
- **Run:** The Run stage varies for each experiment type and involves executing the tasks necessary to run the experiment's test cases on the platform.
 - o Certain values cannot be determined while the platform administrator defines the tasks involved in a test case's execution. Examples include the Execution ID, which depends on the number of previously executed experiments on the platform, and the location of an experiment execution's temporary folder, which is created at run-time. Other values may depend on the output from external applications. Therefore, the ELCM provides a set of 'placeholders.' These placeholders follow a predefined format, consisting of a known identifier enclosed in specific characters: a known identifier enclosed in curly or square brackets, preceded by '@', to ease their detection.
 - ExecutionId: Unique ID of the experiment execution.
 - TempFolder: Path to the temporary folder created exclusively for use of the current experiment executor.
 - Application: The contents of the `Application` field in the Experiment Descriptor.
 - JSON Parameters: The complete `Parameters` dictionary of the Experiment Descriptor, encoded in JSON format.

- `ReservationTime` and `ReservationTimeSeconds`: The value of the `ReservationTime` field of the Experiment Descriptor.
- `TapFolder` and `TapResults`: Paths to the folders where the OpenTAP instance and result output reside, as set in the configuration of the ELCM.

It is also possible to expand the values contained in the `Parameters` dictionary independently, using the following expressions:

- `@[Params.key]`: The value of `key` in the dictionary, or `<<UNDEFINED>>` if not found.
- `@[Params.key:default]`: The value of `key` in the dictionary, or `default` if not found.

Additionally, platform administrators have access to Tasks that are able to generate new (key, value) pairs at runtime, either with a fixed value, a value extracted from a file or taken from a previous task. Once a value has been published using either of these methods, it becomes available for variable expansion using the following expressions:

- `@[key]` or `@[Publish.key]`: Expands to the value of `key` if defined, `<>` otherwise
- `@[key:default]` or `@[Publish.key:default]`: Expands to the value of `key` if defined, or `default`.

- **Post-Run:** During this stage, the resources used by an experiment are released.

3.3.3 ADMINISTRATION INTERFACE

The ELCM includes an administration Interface, a web application developed using Flask, providing a unified interface for platform administrators. This interface allows them to monitor the execution status of an active experiment and track the usage of physical resources on the platform. Additionally, through this interface, administrators can cancel an experiment's execution and review the generated execution logs.

Running Experiments:

(Idle)

Next execution id: 120

Resources

Diagnostics

Figure 7: ELCM Administration Interface

3.3.4 PLATFORM REGISTRY

The Platform Registry defines the functionality and behaviour of a facility and consists of a set of YAML configuration files distributed across four folders alongside the ELCM files. These folders are:

- **TestCases:** Contains information about the available test cases that can be run in the facility.
- **UEs:** Contains specific actions required for using and releasing specific equipment of the facility during the execution of test cases.
- **Resources:** Describes certain facility equipment, particularly those that can only be used by a single experiment at a time.
- **Scenarios:** Contains additional configuration values that can be set during the deployment of a network configuration.

3.3.5 ELCM CONFIGURATION FILES

The contents of the 'UEs' and 'TestCases' YAML files outline the behaviour of the platform when an experiment execution request is received. The ELCM loads the contents of all YAML files in the folders 'UEs' and 'TestCases' at startup and whenever the 'Reload facility' button on the administration dashboard is pressed. The dashboard also displays a validation log ('Facility log'), to assist in detecting errors in a test case or a UE configuration.

The files in both folders share a similar format, containing a main dictionary key that defines the name of the test case or the UE. This key includes the set of actions to perform when the UE is in use or the test case is being executed. For test cases, the configuration files contain additional keys to define the type of experiment (standard, custom, public, private, or distributed), the available configuration parameters (for custom experiments), and the contents of the Grafana dashboard. An important field in every task definition is the 'Order' value, used during the composition process to generate the final list of actions to execute.

3.3.6 RESOURCES AND SCENARIOS

The files in the Resources folder describe specific physical or logical equipment that cannot be shared among multiple experiments simultaneously. For instance, a UE configuration file for a specific mobile phone is typically linked to one resource file, ensuring that the phone is used by only one experiment at a time. Another example is the use of a particular probe during a specific type of experiment.

Resource definition files contain the following keys:

- **Id:** A unique Resource ID used to identify the resource during test case execution.
- **Name:** The name of the resource, visible on the ELCM dashboard.
- **Icon:** The resource icon is also visible on the ELCM dashboard.

Required resources are configured per task. When an experiment execution request is received, the ELCM generates a list of all required resources for all tasks in the experiment (either from a test case or UE definition). When an experiment starts, these resources are locked, preventing other experiments with common requirements from executing until the running experiment finishes and the resources are released.

In the ELCM context, a Scenario is a set of configuration values used to further customize the network's behaviour. These files contain a dictionary with a single key defining the scenario name. The value associated with this key is another dictionary that includes a collection of values to be customized for the scenario.

3.3.7 EXPERIMENT REGISTRY

The Experiment Registry holds information about the execution of each experiment. This includes logs, additional metadata such as start and end times, the final execution status of each stage, and certain files generated by the executed tasks. The Experiment Registry also supports various endpoints of the Open APIs, such as those enabling the retrieval of experiment logs.

3.3.8 GRAFANA DASHBOARD GENERATOR

The ELCM can request the creation of custom dashboards from a running Grafana instance, allowing experimenters to review the results generated by an experiment. To generate these dashboards, the ELCM uses information from the Facility Registry, from which platform administrators can define various Grafana panels.

The parameters that can be used to specify the contents and visualization format of each panel are the following:

- **Type (String):** Panel type. Available values are 'SingleStat' (gauges, numeric values) and 'Graph' (time series graph).
- **Name (Optional) (String):** name of the panel, if not set a default name will be generated from the measurement and field values.
- **Measurement (String):** Measurement name
- **Field (String):** Field Name
- **Unit (Optional) (String):** Results unit
- **Size (List[int]) (String):** Size of the panel (height, width)
- **Position (List[int]):** Panel position in the dashboard (x,y)
- **Color (List[int]):** Graph or text colors. For Gauges this is the list of 3 colors, otherwise a single value.
- **Lines (Graph)(Boolean):** True to display as line graph, False to display as bars

- Percentage (Graph)(Boolean): Whether the graph represents a percentage or not.
- Interval (Graph)(Optional)(String): Time interval of the graph. If not set, the default Grafana interval will be used.
- Dots (Graph)(Boolean): Display dots along with the graph or bar.
- Gauge (SingleStat)(Boolean): True to display as a gauge, false to display as a single numeric value.
- MaxValue(Optional)(Float): Maximum expected value of the gauge, 100 if not set.

MinValue(Optional)(Float): Minimum expected value of the gauge, 0 if not set.

3.4 INTEGRATION WITH THE GLOBAL PLATFORM

As shown in Figure 3, the Portal and the ELCM will be deployed inside the trial network, and an instance of InfluxDB will be used to store the measurements collected during the experiment as it is executed via the ELCM. There is also a Grafana instantiation for the visualization of the data stored in the InfluxDB. The ELCM should contain the plugins needed to configure and control the trial network's resources and also the probes. A plugin is a software component that exposes an API to manage the associated resource or probe. If the use case under test offers an interface for its configuration and control, a plugin could also be developed to automate its operation.

Figure 8: Integration with the Global Platform

The tasks for collecting the measurement/data provided by the different resources of the trial network will be part of the test case. All the measurements will be collected and injected into the influx DB deployed in the trial network as part of the ELCM. The injection of the data into the InfluxDB is triggered by the ELCM, but the measurements can be injected directly by the resources that are under the control of the ELCM, or alternatively the ELCM can retrieve the data and inject it into the InfluxDB. Figure 6 shows an extract of a test case that uses a task of type Run.CsvToInflux injects a CSV file that has been retrieved by the ELCM in the previous task into the InfluxDB. When executing a TAP test plan, it is TAP (as the one shown in Figure 7) responsible for injecting the data into the database is

TAP. In both cases, ExecutionID is used for the task. The TrialNetworkID will be used as a mandatory parameter in all the tasks injecting data.

```
Sequence:
- Order: 20
  Task: Run.CliExecute
  Config:
    Parameters: plink -ssh 10.11.32.XXX -l admin -pw hello -batch -t "sh ./configure_telegraph.sh "@{ExecutionID}""
    CWD: C:/ELCM/Experiment
- Order: 21
  Task: Run.CliExecute
  Config:
    Parameters: plink -ssh 10.11.32.XXX -l admin -pw hello -batch -t "cat edgeping_ping.csv" > edgeping.csv
    #Parameters: 'echo'
    CWD: C:/ELCM/Experiment
- Order: 30
  Task: Run.CsvToInflux
  Config:
    ExecutionId: "@{ExecutionID}"
    CSV: "C:/ELCM/Experiment/TESTTESTping.csv" # Replace with the location of the file
    Measurement: ADB_Ping_Agent
    Delimiter: ','
    Timestamp: 'Timestamp'
    Convert: True
```

Figure 9: Extract of a test case

```
Version: 2
Name: PING
Sequence:
- Order: 5
  Task: Run.TapExecute
  Config:
    TestPlan: "C:/Program Files/OpenTAP/tabPlans/PINGlocal.TapPlan"
    #Measurement: Test231031IPERF
  Externals:
    Device ID: "@{DeviceId}"
    Execution ID: "@{ExecutionID}"
    Iterations: 1
Standard: True
Distributed: False
Dashboard:
- Name: "UE: RoundTrip Time"
  Measurement: "ADB_Ping_Agent"
  Field: "Delay (ms)"
  Unit: ms
  Type: Graph
  Interval: 1s
  Order: ASC
  Size: [9, 12]
  Position: [8, 0]
  Lines: True
  Percentage: False
```

Figure 10: Test case based on TAP test plan

In both cases, the measurements injected have to include the two mandatory tasks, the ExecutionID and the TrialNetwork ID.

4 CURRENT OPEN DATASET REPOSITORY

The 6G-SANDBOX intends to make measurement datasets from the platform openly accessible whenever possible, with the same approach applied to experimental data. However, fully opening experimental data can be more challenging, particularly when experimenters are testing new technologies. While the developments outlined in the current deliverable are ongoing, the consortium has made the data from the platform benchmarking work in WP5 available in Zenodo, with each platform maintaining its own repository.

Each platform has its own data set linked with Zenodo as follows:

- Athens facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373419>
- Berlin facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373435>
- Malaga facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373308>
- Oulu facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373457>

5 CONCLUSIONS

Throughout the document, the mechanisms developed in the project to store and manage the measurements of the experiments were explained. These mechanisms include an open data structure in addition to tools to generate the data from these measurements in a repository. The repository is intended to serve as a valuable resource for researchers, network architects, and technology developers, providing access to empirical data that covers a wide range of scenarios related to the 6GSandbox trial networks. The target is to foster a collaborative environment where academia and industry can come together to share insights, develop solutions, and accelerate the adoption of advanced network technologies.

The document also highlighted the potential impacts of these mechanisms and efforts on future network designs. Through this repository, the project contributes to the foundational knowledge needed to support the next generation of mobile network infrastructure.

ANNEX 1: SOURCE CODE EXAMPLES FOR NAC PLATFORM

CONFIGURATION OF NAC SERVER

Example of the configuration file for the NaC server:

```
{
  "nacService": {
    "port": 8000
  },
  "nacDb": {
    "host": "127.0.0.1",
    "port": 3306,
    "user": "nacuser",
    "password": "****",
    "database": "nac_demolab"
  },
  "influxDb": {
    "version": 2,
    "host": "172.21.32.4",
    "port": 8086,
    "org": "nokia-6gsandbox",
    "token": "N8skhsDCi49ZqnG1w0C-*****20UJierOZncmCDAAdG92Bu9EL4NuNtp8QpyhKfy_-Xz9SN1rg-DQLzA==",
    "bucket": "6gsandbox"
  },
  "capifService": {
    "http_host": "capifcore",
    "http_port": "8080",
    "https_host": "capifcore",
    "https_port": "443",
    "ssh_user": "user",
    "ssh_password": "****"
  }
}
```

CONFIGURATION OF NAC CLIENT

Example of the configuration file for the NaC client:

```
[NacService]
host = 127.0.0.1
port = 8000
username = mt9
password = ***

[CapifService]
http_host = capifcore
http_port = 8080
https_host = capifcore
https_port = 443
username = api_user_1
password = ***
invoker_id = 803d4f280*****db170773887
api_name = nac_api
```

NAC PYTHON API CLIENT

Methods related to NaCapi in charge of the management of KPIs (NaC server release 5.1.0).

Insert KPIs:

```
KPI_send(self, KPI_family, KPI_id, KPI_value, **kwargs) -> list
    Send a set of KPI values to the Influx measurement 'KPI_family', tagged with 'KPI_id'.

Parameters
-----
KPI_family : str
    Identifier of the set of related KPIs. Corresponds to the Influx measurement that
    stores the requested KPIs.

KPI_id : str
    Unique identifier of the requested set of KPIs, inside the KPI_familii. Corresponds
    to the Influx tag 'object' inside
    the measurement 'KPI_family'.

KPI_value : dict
    Object of data values as 'key:value' pair

Raises
-----
ApiException
    401 - Unauthorized to send KPI data
```

Read KPIs:

```
KPI_get(self, KPI_family, KPI_id, tstamp_beg, tstamp_end) -> list
    Get the KPIs from the Influx measurement 'KPI_family', corresponding to indicated time
    range (tstamp_beg, tstamp_end).

Parameters
-----
KPI_family : str
    Identifier of the set of related KPIs. Corresponds to the Influx measurement that
    stores the requested KPIs.

KPI_id : str
    Unique identifier of the requested set of KPIs, inside the KPI_familii. Corresponds
    to the Influx tag 'object' inside
    the measurement 'KPI_family'.

tstamp_beg : datetime
    Beginning of the KPI data block to be returned, in local time format ('YYYY-MM-DD
    HH:MM:SS').

tstamp_end : datetime
    End of the KPI data block to be returned, in local time format ('YYYY-MM-DD
    HH:MM:SS').

    In any case, if the requested KPI block exceeds 24 hours in duration, an error will
    be returned
```

Raises

ApiException

- 400 - Date time interval **is not** valid
- 400 - Date time interval **is** greater than 24h
- 404 - No KPI '**KPI_family**' data found, **or** insufficient permissions

```
KPI_last_before_get(self, KPI_family, KPI_id, tstamp) -> list
```

Get the last KPIs values before '**tstamp**' from the Influx measurement '**KPI_family**'.

Parameters

KPI_family : **str**

Identifier of the **set** of related KPIs. Corresponds to the Influx measurement that stores the requested KPIs.

KPI_id : **str**

Unique identifier of the requested **set** of KPIs, inside the KPI_familiiy. Corresponds to the Influx tag '**object**' inside the measurement '**KPI_family**'.

tstamp : **datetime**

Time before which the last values of the KPIs are requested to be returned, **in** local time format ('**YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS**').

Raises

ApiException

- 400 - Date time interval **is not** valid
- 404 - No KPI '**KPI_family**' data found, **or** insufficient permissions

```
KPI_last_get(self, KPI_family, KPI_id) -> list
```

Get the last KPIs values available **from** the Influx measurement '**KPI_family**'.

Parameters

KPI_family : **str**

Identifier of the **set** of related KPIs. Corresponds to the Influx measurement that stores the requested KPIs.

KPI_id : **str**

Unique identifier of the requested **set** of KPIs, inside the KPI_familiiy. Corresponds to the Influx tag '**object**' inside the measurement '**KPI_family**'.

Raises

ApiException

- 404 - No KPI '**KPI_family**' data found, **or** insufficient permissions

OUTPUT RESULTS

Insert KPIs:

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint
import random

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()

print(f'\n##### Send KPIs:', flush=True)
for i in range(10):
    row = {"kpi1":i, "kpi2":random.random()} *
100, "kpi3": "", "kpi4": "test_agv_" + str(random.randint(1,10))}
    try:
        pprint(api.KPI_send("AGV_KPIs", "agv1", row))
    except Exception as e:
        print(e)
```

Output:

```
$ python test_send_kpis.py

##### Send KPIs:
{'code': 'OK', 'message': 'KPIs inserted'}
```

Read KPIs (KPI_last_get()):

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()
print(f'\n##### Get KPIs:', flush=True)
try:
    pprint(api.KPI_last_get("AGV_KPIs", "agv1"))
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

Output:

```
$ python test_1_get_kpis.py
```

```
##### Get KPIs:
[{'kpi1': '9',
  'kpi2': '30.537528515287804',
  'kpi3': '',
  'kpi4': 'test_agv_5',
  'name': 'uma-AGV_KPIs',
  'object': 'agv1',
  'time': '2024-03-13T10:23:33.425'}]
```

Read KPIs (KPI_get()):

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()
print(f'\n##### Get KPIs:', flush=True)
try:
    pprint(api.KPI_get("AGV_KPIs", "agv1", "2024-03-13 00:00:00", "2024-03-13 23:59:59"))
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

Output:

```
$ python test_2_get_kpis.py

##### Get KPIs:
[{'kpi1': '0',
  'kpi2': '74.00248887938595',
  'kpi3': '',
  'kpi4': 'test_agv_10',
  'name': 'uma-AGV_KPIs',
  'object': 'agv1',
  'time': '2024-03-13T10:23:32.225'},
 {'kpi1': '1',
  'kpi2': '7.055241562643078',
  'kpi3': '',
  'kpi4': 'test_agv_10',
  'name': 'uma-AGV_KPIs',
  'object': 'agv1',
  'time': '2024-03-13T10:23:32.361'},
 {'kpi1': '2',
  'kpi2': '21.24250109993895',
  'kpi3': '',
  'kpi4': 'test_agv_9',
  'name': 'uma-AGV_KPIs',
  'object': 'agv1',
  'time': '2024-03-13T10:23:32.495'}
...
]
```

Read KPIs (KPI_last_before_get()):

```
from __future__ import print_function
from nac_client import NacApi
from pprint import pprint

# Create instance of the NaC API class:
api = NacApi()
print(f'\n##### Get KPIs:', flush=True)
try:
    pprint(api.KPI_last_before_get("AGV_KPIs", "agv1", "2024-03-13 10:23:33"))
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
```

Output:

```
$ python test_3_get_kpis.py

##### Get KPIs:
[{'kpi1': '5',
  'kpi2': '26.111144854911174',
  'kpi3': '',
  'kpi4': 'test_agv_4',
  'name': 'uma-AGV_KPIs',
  'object': 'agv1',
  'time': '2024-03-13T10:23:32.895'}]
```